

The “Centrally Inscribed Square” Triangle

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This is about such isosceles triangle where one of its inscribed squares is central to its circumscribed circle. Two brand new triangle’s centers are proposed as well.

Here we would like to describe a triangle where one of its inscribed squares [1] shares the same center with its circumscribed circle. Such isosceles triangle can also be seen as analogous to the common equilateral triangle where its incircle is always central to its circumscribed circle. A picture¹ of the triangle in question is shown below

The relationⁱ between radius r of the circle and side k of the square of the given triangle, after few steps, reads

$$(r - k/2)^3 = (k/2)^2(r + k/2).$$

* [Wave Cosmodynamics](#)

¹ By [GeoGebra](#)

For example, in case $k = 2$ the cubic equation [2] finally gets an explicit form

$$r^3 - 3r^2 + 2r - 2 = 0$$

with a real solution $r = 2.5213797\dots$. The ratio between the base side and height of the triangle can, in general, be expressed as

$$k/(r - k/2) = 4 : 3.042759\dots$$

For the sake of practicality the ratio might be set to $4 : 3$. Now we can also calculate the apex angle² of this triangle, i.e.

$$\alpha = 2\arctan(2/3.042759) \approx 66.63369^\circ$$

Let us notice that its complementary angle of about 23.37 degrees reminds of the actual value of Earth's axial tilt which is 23.44° [3].

Finally, the author would like to suggest two new points laying on the Kiepert hyperbola [4] of a triangle. One would be based on the center of the inscribed square of our triangle and the second on its apex. Their constructionsⁱⁱ are obvious.

Acknowledgments

The author cordially dedicates this work to the memory of a late dear friend Nermin Jakirlić. Moreover, the very theme was only a part of an intense exchange mostly during '80s.

As a nonetheless valuable part of this work the author recognizes the long standing, open minded as well as deeply symbolical observations of his dear sister Dragana Sandalj.

References

[1] Inscribed square in a triangle,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inscribed_square_in_a_triangle
Triangle Square Inscribing,
<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/TriangleSquareInscribing.html>

[2] Cubic equation,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cubic_equation
Weisstein, Eric W. "[Cubic Formula](#)". *MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource*

² Hence, the base angle is $\beta = (180 - \alpha)/2 = 56.68315^\circ$

[3] Axial tilt,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Axial_tilt

[4] Weisstein, Eric W. "[Kiepert Hyperbola](#)". *MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource*

[5] Fermat point,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fermat_point
[Cut The Knot - The Fermat Point and Generalizations](#)

Addendum

Two interesting, mutually equivalent classical constructions and related apex angle are presented in no wards.

April, 2025

i Obvious first step, based on the theorems of Tales and Pithagoras, is

$$\sqrt{r^2 - (k/2)^2}/(r + k/2) = (k/2)/(r - k/2)$$

ii Those two (even four) are a clear analogy of the well known Fermat-Torricelli and Napoleon points [5].